
THE IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGIES ON LANGUAGE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

Technology is one of the big parts of educational system, that language instructors should be well educated and knowledgeable to educate others, at the same they have to acquire the skill of retaining student’s attention and deliver content in an effective way, as teaching is important profession. Information technologies has a huge impact on teaching itself and the research of the role of IT in the process of teaching foreign languages is devoted to the works of many scientists, even gave rise to a new direction in the methodology – computational linguo-didactics

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Nowadays the role of technology is rising in every sphere, and teaching of foreign languages is not exception. Information technologies has a huge impact on teaching itself and the research of the role of IT in the process of teaching foreign languages is devoted to the works of many scientists, even gave rise to a new direction in the methodology – computational linguo-didactics. In this period of time, knowing only the language itself, its content is not enough to conduct effective lesson, for this reason every language instructor should know how to use IT tools in ones lesson. On the other hand, whereas before, most studies were conducted to prove that the use of IT allows you to achieve significant pedagogical progress. However, now it should be stated that it is necessary to minimize the negative impact of the same IT on the learning process at school. A study conducted by American scientists showed that a person's IQ stopped growing and even began to decline and in the conditions of global globalization, the "Angloization" of the media and limitless opportunities, it would be logical to expect an increase in the level of knowledge of foreign languages, but this does not happen, moreover, this level is getting lower from year to year

Teaching languages using technologies makes the lesson more effective, for example even the ordinary projector is tool which is essential while conducting the class, grapes students' attention, as instructor may just prepare power point presentations with activities. G.N. Wikramanayake said in his research "Advances in digital technology have opened up many avenues of learning. Technology has made information accessible / transmittable from anywhere and by / to all groups of people. Education has reached most parts of the world and ICT has become an integral part of human life" (2014).

Technologies, internet have own pros and cons, if we talk about negative sides, they can be used in the class by students themselves, they can just stuck surfing social sites, instead of following the instructor. Razifah binti Othman mentioned in his research that “internet has become an amazing potential for learning, entertainment and socializing gizmo. It has encouraged teenagers and children to participate and express themselves for extraordinary source of information and self-improvement ” (2019), about impacts of internet.

Problems can be noticed when learners are exposed to internet, technology without any regulation and control, they tend to be hooked on the computer for the amusement offered by the internet, they can surf to find out what is available and can be offered online, like songs, movies, chatting that can result not to achieve growth during the sessions and development stage.

Teachers, especially language instructors should be well educated and knowledgeable to educate others, at the same they have to acquire the skill of retaining student's attention and deliver content in an effective way, as teaching is important profession. But in 21st century being well- educative is not enough for teachers, they should also know IT. In this period, technologies in teaching and learning are considered as one of the big parts of conducting the lessons. Technology is useful to convey instant messages and well as to make people be aware current local and international, it becomes an effective form of education.

In the research that was done by Razifah binti Othman et el. (2019) mentioned that “In the modern global learning environment teacher's role shifts from "dispenser of information" to "facilitator of learning" as he has only to guide the active students who are involved in using the e-learning material. Classrooms have been fully equipped with permanent multimedia projectors and computers and the facilitator needs to access the e-learning system through the Intranet. Teachers should not control the learning process as well as they should allow students to perform

collaborative work and make some decisions on their own”. Using computers for education is gradually wide spreading, these benefits now enjoyed by a small fraction of the availability among the population, but soon it will encourage others to join and enjoy the benefits of technology.

The use of ICT makes the teaching and learning process easier, more interesting and effective, it is obvious that the usage of it will increase the level of achievements and understanding, as it gives precise and realistic view of subject matter. Besides, the colorful colors, various visuals, sounds attract students in the class, making learning session to be more engaging and increasing the focus of students on instructor.

Using the internet can intensify a social structure, for example, competitive games will produce one’s strong motivation to succeed, while the opponent fails. Cooperative games and activities are focused to inspire sharing, trust building, accept fails, to learn and practice positive social behaviors, they also train learners to encourage and help others.

Technology and teaching should be rolled on one stage, as the are connected with each other, conducting the class using IT appropriately is also high level of education, that every instructor should competitive at both of them.

REFERENCES

1. Ahmed, A. (2010) “The Implementation of ICT Strategy at Sudanese Secondary Schools. PhD thesis of Computer Integrated Education. Sudan University of Science and Technology. Not Published.”
2. Daniels, J.S. (2002) “Foreword in Information and Communication Technology in Education–A Curriculum for Schools and Programme for Teacher Development. Paris: UNESCO.”
3. Razifah binti Othman¹, Kamal Fahrulrazy Rahim, Rabiatul Adawiyah binti Kamarulzaman, Dia Widyawati Amat Rohana Sham (2019) “Malaysian E Commerce Journal (MECJ)” 2019
4. Skarderud, F(2003). Shame in Cyberspace. Relationships without faces: the e-media and eating disorders. *European Eating Disorders Review*, 11(3), [155–169].
5. Valkenburg, P.M., Peter, J. (2007). Online communication and adolescent well-being: Testing the stimulation versus displacement hypothesis. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 12, [1169– 1182].